

Considering the $\kappa - \mu$ fading channels adopted in multiple antennas downlink non-orthogonal multiple access

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ABSTRACT

Massive connectivity and effective spectrum usage have become more important as the use of wireless communication devices and networks has grown dramatically. The approach of non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) is advocated as a viable solution for meeting consumers' current needs. The signals are overlaid with various power levels for each user in a NOMA-assisted system, and then broadcast to the receiver. SIC (successive interference cancellation) is used by the receiver to discriminate and get the needed signal. Until far, most studies have concentrated on SIC with ideal features, with only a handful focusing on SIC with imperfect qualities (ipSIC). While the perfect SIC (pSIC) represents the ideal condition of no data loss and no external sounds, the ipSIC represents data transfer in a real-time context. In this research, we will assess the system performance metrics of the investigated NOMA system in the presence of ipSIC and compare them to the performance of the same user's pSIC. We define channels as $\kappa - \mu$ fading distributions, which is more essential. For two destinations, we construct accurate outage probability formulas. Meanwhile, Monte-Carlo simulations are run to ensure that the mathematical expressions derived are genuine.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing appetite for the internet of things (IoT) and mobile internet is behind the design push for innovative future wireless communication networks that satisfy high spectral and connectivity efficiency [1]–[3]. Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) is one of the technologies proposed to address spectral efficiency and mass connectivity challenges in future network systems [1]–[3]. Unlike existing orthogonal multiple access (OMA), NOMA accommodates more users by utilizing non-orthogonal resource allocation [1]–[8]. NOMA is divided in two sub-categories: power and code-based NOMA [1], [3], [5]. In this study, we have mainly concerned with power-domain NOMA which typically serves multiple users by grouping and superposing users' data signals at the transmitters. Users experiencing dissimilar channel conditions are usually grouped. Hence, far users experiencing poor channel conditions are allocated greater transmit power and in each group, while the near receiver utilizes successive interference cancellation (SIC) to decode the data transmitted signal to the far user. SIC helps to eliminate interference, thus, users with better channel gain do not require high transmit power to achieve good throughput [9].

Several studies have investigated the performance benefits of power-domain in various NOMA-assisted

communication networks. For example, [10] studied the outage of NOMA assisted downlink multi-cell millimeter-wave (mmWave) network under Nakagami- m fading. The authors numerically proved that NOMA outperforms OMA in multi-cell mmWave systems. Zhang *et al.* in [11], the authors demonstrated the individual outage rate of NOMA's fading and power split configurations in cognitive hybrid satellite-ground networks reliant on amplify and forward (AF) procedures. In particular, the ground network channels followed Nakagami- m distribution whilst the satellite links followed generalized shadowed-Rician fading. Differently, the authors in [12], compared the outage and throughput performance of two popular NOMA decoding techniques, SIC and joint-decoding (JD), in uplink machine-to-machine (M2M) communications. Numerical results showed that SIC has similar performance to JD when transmitting powers and traffic load over frequency-flat block-fading multiple access channels are low but underperforms under higher transmit powers or frequency-selectivity conditions. In similar work, in [13], the authors confirmed that NOMA outperforms OMA in enhancing the spectral efficiency of K-tier heterogeneous networks (HetNets).

Another key technology has already deployed in long term evolution (LTE-advanced) and 5G is massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) [14], [15]. In this work, they examined the utilization of power-domain NOMA at base stations with multiple antennas. Various works on multiple antennas aided NOMA have focused on perfect SIC such as [16]–[26] whereas only a few have focused on imperfect SIC (ipSIC) as in [27]–[29]. While the perfect SIC (pSIC) represents the ideal condition of no data loss and no external sounds, the ipSIC represents data transfer in a real-time context.

Motivated by recent studies, just a few works have examined how single-input single-output (SISO) downlink NOMA systems perform in general fading channels. For instance, in [30], the authors investigated the impact of residual transceiver hardware impairments on cooperative SISO NOMA under generic $\alpha - \mu$ fading channels. The authors also proposed exact asymptotic formulas for outage probability (OP), ergodic capacity, and energy efficiency to characterize the system performance. Le *et al.* in [31], the authors studied the uplink performance of SISO NOMA systems subject to imperfect SIC and delay constraints over a wide range of fading composite fading channels like lognormal-Nakagami- m , $K_G, \eta - \mu$, Nakagami- q (Hoyt), $\kappa - \mu$, Nakagami- n (Rician), Nakagami- m , and Rayleigh fading channels. The authors derived exact expressions of OP, throughput, and capacity based on Meijer-G functions. Moreover, [32], the authors considered OP for downlink and uplink multi-user SISO power-domain NOMA network where users can be subject to one of the fading distributions mentioned in [31]. ElHalawany *et al.* in [33], the authors also developed exact expressions for ergodic capacity, OP and bit error rate (BER) for a two-user NOMA-aided SISO downlink framework under $\kappa - \mu$ shadowing.

Differently, this paper provides a scheme to highlight the different OP performance of two users separated by an obstruction in a multiple-input single-output (MISO) NOMA network utilizing perfect and imperfect SIC under $\kappa - \mu$ fading channels. Our contributions are listed as being as: We investigate power-domain NOMA by examining the downlink OP performance under $\kappa - \mu$ fading channels using perfect and imperfect SIC. We formulate exact OP formulas subject to the power allocation coefficients constraints. We evaluate outage under $\kappa - \mu$ fading channels to show how perfect and imperfect SIC guarantees operation in the downlink when there is an obstruction between the two users. Simulation results demonstrate that imperfect SIC, in terms of the OP, outperforms perfect SIC.

The remainder of this document is formatted as being as. The downlink power-domain NOMA with generalized channels is described in section 2. In part 3, we look at the outage performance of a power-domain NOMA scenario. In part 4, we present comprehensive numerical simulations, and section 5 ends the article.

2. DESCRIPTION OF DOWNLINK NOMA WITH GENERALIZED CHANNELS

Figure 1 shows a base station (BS) equipped with N antennas to serve two NOMA users, U_1 and U_2 . Particularly, we assume that the BS is equipped with n antennas in which $n = [1, 2, \dots, N]$. The channel gain of links $BS - U_1$ and $BS - U_2$ are defined as $g_{n,1}$ and $g_{n,2}$, respectively. In this study, the BS transmits the superposed information $s = \sqrt{Pb_1}s_1 + \sqrt{Pb_2}s_2$ to the users (U_1 and U_2), where s_1 and s_2 are U_1 and U_2 the messages, respectively. b_1 and b_2 are the power allocation coefficients subject to $b_2 > b_1$ and $b_2 + b_1 = 1$. P is the BS transmit power. Moreover, U_1 and U_2 receive the superposed signal and loop interference signal simultaneously. The observations at U_1 and U_2 are [34]:

$$y_{n,1} = g_{n,1} \left(\sqrt{Pb_1}s_1 + \sqrt{Pb_2}s_2 \right) + \omega_{n,1}, \quad (1)$$

$$y_{n,2} = g_{n,2} \left(\sqrt{Pb_1} s_1 + \sqrt{Pb_2} s_2 \right) + \omega_{n,2}, \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Downlink NOMA with generalized channels

where $\omega_{n,i} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, N_0)$, for $i = 1, 2$ is the additive complex white gaussian noise (AWGN).

As given (2), U_2 is able to detect s_2 by treating s_1 in (2) as an interference. The instantaneous signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at U_2 from (2) is given as:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2}^n = \frac{\rho b_2 |g_{n,2}|^2}{1 + \rho b_1 |g_{n,2}|^2} = \frac{b_2 \gamma_{n,2}}{1 + b_1 \gamma_{n,2}}, \quad (3)$$

where $\gamma_{n,i} \triangleq \rho |g_{n,i}|^2$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and $\rho = P/N_0$ is the transmit SNR at NOMA users.

As for the detection of s_2 , U_1 first performs SIC that decodes and removes U_2 's message, then proceeds to decode its own message without interference. For this, the instantaneous SINR at U_1 for the detection of s_2 is given as:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2 \rightarrow U_1}^n = \frac{\rho b_2 |g_{n,1}|^2}{1 + \rho b_1 |g_{n,1}|^2} = \frac{b_2 \gamma_{n,1}}{1 + b_1 \gamma_{n,1}}, \quad (4)$$

After the SIC procedure in this context, resulting in a positive residual interference quantity and channel estimation noise without the interference of s_1 with imperfect SIC (ipSIC) and perfect SIC (pSIC), the instantaneous signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at U_1 for the detection of s_1 is represented as [35]:

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}^{n,pSIC} = b_1 \gamma_{n,1}, \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}^{n,ipSIC} = \frac{b_1 \gamma_{n,1}}{1 + \rho |h_I|^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $|h_I|^2 \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \lambda_I)$ in which $0 \leq \lambda_I < 1$ is the level of residual interference caused by imperfect SIC and $\mathcal{CN} \sim (a, b)$ is the complex normal distribution with average a and variance b .

3. ANALYSIS OF OUTAGE PROBABILITY

3.1. The channel model

We set $\gamma_n = \gamma_{n_1} = \gamma_{n_2}$, thus, the probability density function (PDF) of γ_n is given by [36], [37]:

$$p_{\gamma_n}(x | \kappa, \mu, \rho) = \mathcal{G}(\kappa, \mu, \rho) x^{(\mu-1)/2} e^{-\lambda_g x} \mathcal{I}_{\mu-1}(2\sqrt{\kappa\mu\lambda_g x}) \quad , x > 0 \quad (7)$$

where $\lambda_g = \frac{(1+\kappa)\mu}{\rho}$, $\mathcal{G}(\kappa, \mu, \rho) = \frac{\lambda_g^{(\mu+1)/2}}{[\kappa\mu]^{(\mu-1)/2} e^{\kappa\mu}}$, $\kappa > 0$ designates the total power of dominant components and the total power of scattered waves ratio. $\mu > 0$ describes the number of multi-path clusters and $\mathcal{I}_\nu(x)$ denotes the ν -th order modified Bessel function. Similarly, the PDFs of γ_i , $i \in \{1, 2\}$ in $\kappa - \mu$ fading channels can be expressed by $p_{\gamma_i}(x | \kappa_i, \mu_i, \rho)$. For arbitrary values κ and μ , the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of γ_n can be obtained as [38], (31).

$$F_{\gamma_n}(x | \kappa, \mu, \rho) = 1 - \mathcal{Q}_\mu(\sqrt{2\kappa\mu}, \sqrt{2\lambda_g x}) \quad , x > 0 \quad (8)$$

with $\mathcal{Q}_c(a, b) = a^{1-c} \int_b^\infty x^c e^{-(x^2+a^2)/2} \mathcal{I}_{c-1}(ax) dx$ specifies the generalized Marcum Q-function in [39], (4.33). For integer values of μ and with the help of [39], (4.63), $F_{\gamma_n}(x | \kappa, \mu, \rho)$ can be greatly simplified as:

$$F_{\gamma_n}(x | \kappa, \mu, \rho) = e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g x} \sum_{r=\mu}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\lambda_g x}{\kappa\mu} \right)^{r/2} \mathcal{I}_r(2\sqrt{\kappa\mu\lambda_g x}), \quad (9)$$

Utilizing $\mathcal{I}_q(a\sqrt{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a\sqrt{x}/2)^{2n+r}}{n!\Gamma(n+r+1)}$ is the modified Bessel function of the first kind of order q in [40], (8.445), we have:

$$F_{\gamma_n}(x | \kappa, \mu, \rho) = e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g x} \sum_{r=\mu}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} x^{n+r}}{n!\Gamma(n+r+1)}. \quad (10)$$

3.2. Two users outage probability

When the user's rates are determined based on their channel conditions, OP becomes an important metric for performance evaluation. Hence the performance of two users in terms of the OP is obtained in the following way.

Case 1: $0 < \lambda_I \leq 1$, we have the OP with ipSIC for U_1 is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} &= \Pr \left(\max_{n \in N} \{ \tilde{\gamma}_{U_2 \rightarrow U_1}^n \} < \tilde{\varepsilon}_2 \cup \max_{n \in N} \{ \tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}^{n, ipSIC} \} < \tilde{\varepsilon}_1 \right) \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^N \left[1 - \Pr \left(\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2 \rightarrow U_1}^n \geq \tilde{\varepsilon}_2, \tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}^{n, ipSIC} \geq \tilde{\varepsilon}_1 \right) \right] \\ &= \left[1 - \Pr \left(\gamma_1 \geq \tilde{\eta}_2, \gamma_1 \geq \tilde{\eta}_1 (1 + \rho |h_I|^2) \right) \right]^N, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{\varepsilon}_i = 2^{2R_i} - 1$, for $i = 1, 2$, R_i being the target rate at U_i , $\tilde{\eta}_2 = \frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_2}{b_2 - \tilde{\varepsilon}_2 b_1}$ and $\tilde{\eta}_1 = \frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}_1}{b_1}$. Assuming $\tilde{\eta}_1 (1 + \rho |h_I|^2) \gg \tilde{\eta}_2$, $\mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC}$ can be calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} &= \left[1 - \Pr \left(\gamma_{n,1} \geq \tilde{\eta}_1 (1 + \rho |h_I|^2) \right) \right]^N \\ &= \left\{ 1 - \int_0^\infty f_{|h_I|^2}(x) [1 - F_{\gamma_{n,1}}(\tilde{\eta}_1 (1 + \rho x))] dx \right\}^N. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

3.2.1. Proposition

The exact OP with ipSIC at the user U_1 is written as:

$$\mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} = \left[e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1} \sum_{r=\mu}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{q=0}^{n+r} \binom{n+r}{q} \frac{q! \kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_1^{n+r} \lambda_I^q \rho^q}{n!\Gamma(n+r+1) (1 + \lambda_I \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1 \rho)^{q+1}} \right]^N, \quad (13)$$

where $\Gamma(\bullet)$ is the Gamma function [40], (8.310).

3.2.2. Proof of proposition

From (12), $\mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC}$ is expanded is being as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} &= \left[1 - \int_0^\infty f_{|h_I|^2}(x) dx + \int_0^\infty f_{|h_I|^2}(x) F_{\gamma_{n,1}}(\tilde{\eta}_1(1+\rho x)) dx \right]^N \\ &= \left[1 - \lambda_I \int_0^\infty e^{-\frac{x}{\lambda_I}} dx + \frac{e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1}}{\lambda_I} \sum_{r=\mu}^\infty \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{\kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_1^{n+r}}{n! \Gamma(n+r+1)} \int_0^\infty e^{-x(\frac{1}{\lambda_I} + \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1 \rho)} (1+\rho x)^{n+r} dx \right]^N. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

For the first integral, it equals 1. For the second integral we use Newton’s Binomial Theorem.

$$(x+y)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^{n-k} y^k = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^k y^{n-k}. \tag{15}$$

Hence (14) is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} = \frac{e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1}}{\lambda_I} \sum_{r=\mu}^\infty \sum_{n=0}^\infty \sum_{q=0}^{n+r} \binom{n+r}{q} \frac{\kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_1^{n+r} \rho^q}{n! \Gamma(n+r+1)} \int_0^\infty e^{-x(\frac{1}{\lambda_I} + \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1 \rho)} x^q dx. \tag{16}$$

Using [40], (3.351.3), we have close-form outage probability with ipSIC of U_1 given as:

$$\mathcal{P}_1^{ipSIC} = \left[e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1} \sum_{r=\mu}^\infty \sum_{n=0}^\infty \sum_{q=0}^{n+r} \binom{n+r}{q} \frac{q! \kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_1^{n+r} \lambda_I^q \rho^q}{n! \Gamma(n+r+1) (1 + \lambda_I \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_1 \rho)^{q+1}} \right]^N. \tag{17}$$

Based on the aforementioned results, the proof is complete.

Case 2: $\lambda_I = 0$, $\mathcal{P}_1^{pSIC}$ is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_1^{pSIC} &= \Pr \left(\max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{ \tilde{\gamma}_{U_2 \rightarrow U_1}^n \} < \tilde{\epsilon}_2 \cup \max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{ \tilde{\gamma}_{U_1}^{n,pSIC} \} < \tilde{\epsilon}_1 \right) \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^N [1 - \Pr(\gamma_{n,1} \geq \tilde{\eta}_2, \gamma_{n,1} \geq \tilde{\eta}_1)] \\ &= [1 - \Pr(\gamma_{n,1} \geq \tilde{\eta}_{\max})]^N \\ &= [F_{\gamma_{n,1}}(\tilde{\eta}_{\max})]^N, \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where $\tilde{\eta}_{\max} = [\tilde{\eta}_1, \tilde{\eta}_2]^+$ in which $[a, b]^+ = \max(a, b)$.

Applying (8), (10), and (18) can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_1^{pSIC} &\stackrel{\mu \in \mathbb{Q}}{=} \left[\mathcal{Q}_\mu \left(\sqrt{2\kappa\mu}, \sqrt{2\lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_{\max}} \right) \right]^N \\ &\stackrel{\mu \in \mathbb{N}}{=} \left[e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_{\max}} \sum_{r=\mu}^\infty \sum_{n=0}^\infty \frac{\kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_{\max}^{n+r}}{n! \Gamma(n+r+1)} \right]^N. \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Solving of $\mathcal{P}_1^{pSIC}$ we obtain the closed-form OP at U_2 as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}_2 &= \Pr \left(\max_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{ \tilde{\gamma}_{U_2}^n \} < \tilde{\epsilon}_2 \right) \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^N [1 - \Pr(\tilde{\gamma}_{U_2}^n \geq \tilde{\epsilon}_2)] \\ &= [1 - \Pr(\gamma_{n,2} \geq \tilde{\eta}_2)]^N \\ &= [F_{\gamma_{n,2}}(\tilde{\eta}_2)]^N. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Similarly, we obtain the OP of U_2 as:

$$\mathcal{P}_2 \stackrel{\mu \in \mathbb{Q}}{=} \left[\mathcal{Q}_\mu \left(\sqrt{2\kappa\mu}, \sqrt{2\lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_2} \right) \right]^N \stackrel{\mu \in \mathbb{N}}{=} \left[e^{-\kappa\mu - \lambda_g \tilde{\eta}_2} \sum_{r=\mu}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\kappa^n \mu^n \lambda_g^{n+r} \tilde{\eta}_2^{n+r}}{n! \Gamma(n+r+1)} \right]^N. \quad (21)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, $\kappa - \mu$ fading is used; see Table I for a list of examples. We use mathematical derivations to mimic OP and then use Monte-Carlo simulation to check these derivations. Table 2 contains a list of the parameters.

Table 1. The $\kappa - \mu$ distribution yields common fading distributions [41]

Channels	$\kappa - \mu$ Distribution parameters
Rayleigh	$\mu = 1, \kappa \rightarrow 0$
One-sided Gaussian	$\mu = 0.5, \kappa \rightarrow 0$
$\kappa - \mu$	$\mu = \mu, \kappa = \kappa$
Nakagami- m	$\mu = m, \kappa \rightarrow 0$
Rician with parameter K	$\mu = 1, \kappa = K$

Table 2. In the performance evaluation, system parameters were employed [42]

System Parameters	Values
Monte Carlo simulations repeated	10^6 iterations
Antennas of BS	$N = 2$
The power allocation coefficients	$\{b_1, b_2\} = \{0.1, 0.9\}$
The target rate at U_1	$R_1 = 2$ bps/Hz
The target rate at U_2	$R_2 = 1$ bps/Hz
The interference signal's effect level (IS)	$\lambda_I = 0.001$

Figure 2 depicts OP for user U_1 with imperfect SIC versus transmit SNR for different fading channels. From the Figure, we can observe how the level of interference signal λ_I impacts OP. The best OP performance is achieved under Nakagami- m fading channels for both cases of λ_I . Also, the OP curves approach a floor at large SNR values as this is indicative of the error introduced by SIC in general. However, the OP performance curves have different values depending on the λ_I value. The reason is that imperfect SIC under performs in cases of large levels of interference signal as to be expected from the literature.

Figure 3 depicts OP for both user U_1 with perfect and imperfect SIC conditions, and user U_2 versus transmit SNR for different fading channels with $\lambda_I = 0.001$. From the Figure, we can observe how the different values of $\kappa - \mu$ distribution impact OP. The best OP performance is achieved under $(\kappa - \mu) = (2, 0)$ for both U_1 and U_2 . In addition, we can observe that OP for user U_2 does not approach a floor as SIC is not utilized at the user receiver but the OP curves for U_1 approach a floor at large SNR values when perfect SIC is exploited at the receiver.

Figure 4 depicts OP for both user U_1 with perfect and imperfect SIC conditions, and user U_2 versus power allocation b_2 for different values of fading channels with target rates $R_1 = R_2 = 0.5$, $\lambda_I = 0.01$ and $\rho = 15$ dB. From the Figure, we can observe how the different values of $\kappa - \mu$ distribution impact OP. The best OP performance is achieved under $(\kappa - \mu) = (2, 0)$ for both U_1 and U_2 . Moreover, at about $b_2 = 0.65$ the OP for both SIC cases for user U_1 starts performing poorly. This demonstrates the relationship between power allocation coefficients and OP.

Figure 5 depicts OP for both user U_1 with perfect and imperfect SIC conditions, and user U_2 versus varying target rates $R_1 = R_2$, $\lambda_I = 0.01$, $b_1 = 0.05$, $b_2 = 0.95$ and while varying ρ dB. In Figure 5, we can see how the different values of $R_1 = R_2$ and ρ impact OP. The best OP performance is achieved at $R_1 = R_2 = 0.3$ bit/s/Hz for both U_1 and U_2 . Also, for user U_1 the OP hits a ceiling at high $R_1 = R_2$ values.

Figure 2. Probability of U_1 with ipSIC versus ρ [dB] for different fading channels

Figure 3. Outage probability versus ρ [dB] for different fading channels, with $\lambda_I = 0.001$

Figure 4. Outage probability versus b_2 for different values of general fading channel, with $R_1 = R_2 = 0.5$, $\lambda_I = 0.01$ and $\rho = 15$ [dB]

Figure 5. Outage probability versus target rate, with $\lambda_I = 0.01$, $b_1 = 0.05$ and $b_2 = 0.95$

5. CONCLUSION

We studied a NOMA communication network with two users D_1 and D_2 in this study. We also developed mathematical formulae for OP in the case of a receiver with an incomplete SIC. These expressions were simulated using different $\kappa - \mu$ fading distribution channels (which are more generic than particular situations like Rayleigh, Nakagami- m , and Rician fading channels). The additional simulations were done using the general fading distribution of κ and μ as the major discovery. As can be shown from the simulations, imperfect SIC outperforms flawless SIC models.

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